

A Study on Challenges and Opportunities in E-Banking Sector in India

K.Anitha, M.Com [CA],M.Phil.,

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce [CA]

Madurai Sivakasi Nadars Meenakshi Pioneer College for Women

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 3

Month : February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Anitha, K. "A Study on Challenges and Opportunities in E-Banking Sector in India." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S3, 2019, pp. 14–17.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2572407>

Abstract

Banking is the sustenance of a financial system of the country. Banks are the institutional bodies that accept deposits and grant credit to the entities and play a major role in maintaining the economic stature of a country. E-Banking is the one of the major part of E-Financing. Internet banking refers to the deployment over the Internet of retail and wholesale banking services. In India, the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) is the apex banking institution that regulates the monetary policy in the country. E-banking is a safe, fast, easy and efficient electronic service that enables you access to bank account and to carry out online banking services, 24 hours a day, and 7 days a week. With this service we can save our time by carrying out banking transactions at any place and at any time, from our home or office, all we need is internet access. It must be noted, however, that while e-banking provides many benefits to customers and banks, it also aggravates traditional banking risks. This paper is an attempt to study the benefits, challenges and various services given by E-banking. This paper is related to secondary data in nature and information regarding the study is gathered from RBI bulletin, various noticeable journals, newspapers and some research studies. Compared to developed countries, developing countries face many impediments that affect the successful implementation of e-banking initiatives. In this paper, we have identified some obstacles in the Indian context.

Introduction

Banking is the sustenance of a financial system of the country. Banks are the institutional bodies that accept deposits and grant credit to the entities and play a major role in maintaining the economic stature of a country and given importance in the economy, banks are kept under strict regulation in most of the countries. E-Banking is the one of the major part of E-Financing. Internet banking refers to the deployment over the Internet of retail and wholesale banking services. E-Banking uses the web browser for the user interface and the Internet for data transfer and download of software, and so has a potential for reducing maintenance costs. In India, the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) is the apex banking institution that regulates the monetary policy in the country. E-banking is a safe, fast, easy and efficient electronic service that enables you access to bank account and to carry out online banking services, 24 hours a day, and 7 days a week. With this service we can save our time by carrying out banking transactions at any place and at any time, from our home or office, all we need is internet access.

The Indian banking industry has undergone extraordinary rivalry among unconventional banking organizations. The introduction of latest technologies along with the deregulation of the banking sector has attracted new players to make a attack into the industry rapidly and competently. If you consider the present age of banking, online banking has made things much easier and has saved lot of time of Bank employees as well as general public. The traditional way of waiting in a queue and filling up all the forms manually, is no hassle now for transacting with any bank. ICICI was the first bank to introduce internet banking to its customers in 1996 in India. And it provided at slighter internet costs and increased awareness about electronic media and online banking established itself only in 1999. E-banking refers to performing basic banking transactions by the customers through electronic media by using through PC or LAPTOP. The customers can access the banks website for viewing their account details and perform the transactions on account as per their requirement. E-banking is more information based speedy & margin less due to the bang of E-Revolution. Electronic banking, provide various services to their customer such as, mobile banking, internet banking, electronic funds transfer (EFT), Electronic Clearing System (ECS), Immediate Payment Service (IMPS). Each financial institution can determine the types of financial transactions which a customer may transact through online banking, but usually includes obtaining account balances, a list of recent transactions, electronic bill payments, financing loans and funds transfers between a customer's or another's accounts. Most banks set limits on the amounts that may be transacted and other restrictions. Most banks also enable customers to download copies of bank statements, which can be printed at the customer's premises. Some banks also enable customers to download transactions directly into the customers accounting software.

Research Methodology

Objective of the study

1. To study the challenges appeared in E-banking.
2. To learn about the prospects available for E-banking in India.
3. To classify a range of e-banking services/products implemented in India.

The present study is descriptive in nature and information regarding this paper is gathered from RBI bulletin, various noticeable journals, newspapers and some research studies.

E-banking various services in India

The advancement in sophisticated information and communication technology is supporting power for the fast computerization of the banking operations. The online initiation of banking sector is a new paradigm revolution from paper-based transaction to online transaction. Broadly, the levels of banking services offered through INTERNET can be categorized in to three types: (i) The Basic Level Service is the banks websites which disseminate information on different products and services offered to customers and members of public in general. It may receive and reply to customers' queries through e-mail, (ii) In the next level are Simple Transactional Websites which allow customers to submit their instructions, applications for different services, queries on their account balances, etc, but do not permit any fund-based transactions on their accounts, (iii) The third level of Internet banking services are offered by Fully Transactional Websites which allow the customers to operate on their accounts for transfer of funds, payment of different bills, subscribing to other products of the bank and to transact purchase and sale of securities etc,. E-banking enables the following services in India:

- Accurate statement of all means available in our bank account.
- Statement of current account, credits, overdrafts and our deposits.
- Carrying out of national and international transfers in various currencies by NEFT, RTGS.

- Execution of all types of utility bill payments (electricity, water supply, telephone bills, etc.)
- Electronic confirmation for all transactions executed by E-banking.
- Management of credit cards, debit cards, and smart cards.

Security of E-Banking

Authentication: The concern banks use the personal identification number (PIN) and a distinct customer identity number which enables customers to access their accounts transactions.

Privacy: The internet-based banking must ensure that only the right person can access the information in order to ensure online privacy techniques and standard encryption are used while connecting and communication with the bank.

Integrity: Integrity refers to internet banking the security of data and message involves legal and procedural in electronic transaction.

Transaction Conformation: One of the security aspects in internet banking is transaction conformation to display a list of instruction to be sent by the bank before completing the transaction. Identification and Password: Assigning a correct password ensures the only authorization for data access. Further cross checks may be imposed for additional security.

Authorization: Authorization ensures that only a user can access the data to whom the permission has been granted to right to use, read or alter data.

Challenges in E-Banking

This changing financial site brings with a series of questions and challenges regarding the level of security and benefits of E-banking. Some of the challenges are given below.

Operational Risk: Operational risk, also referred to as transactional risk is the most common form of risk associated with E-banking. It takes the form of inaccurate processing of transactions, non enforceability of contracts, compromises in data integrity, data privacy and confidentiality, unauthorized access / intrusion to bank's systems and transactions etc. Such risks can arise out of weaknesses in design, implementation and monitoring of banks' information system. Besides inadequacies in technology, human factors like negligence by customers and employees, fraudulent activity of employees and crackers / hackers etc. can become potential source of operational risk.

Costly Technology: In connection with set up cost e-banking is huge at initial level for acquiring personal computer and other equipments; oneself to do online banking is still not with reach of the middle class & upper middle class customers. The cost of maintenance of all equipments like, modem, routers, bridges and network management systems is very high. The cost of sophisticated hardware and software and skill level of people needed. In Internet banking there is need of skilled employees or knowledgeable professionals to route the banking transactions via internet.

Acceptance of Customer: Proper understanding of the customer is the major aspect of the E-banking. It is known that computer literacy in India is yet very low and is problems in fast acceptance of internet. Attitude of the Indian customer needs to be changed by giving awareness about technical terms in internet banking. However, it supports in the fast changing technical scenario, the obsolesce of technology fast. Hence there is always lack of skilled personal and fear of technology.

Legal Risk: Information technology act provides security & legal framework for e-commerce transactions as well as e-banking. Information technology act or RBI suggested that criterion of Digital Signature Certification Board for authentication of electric records and communication with digital signatures.

Confidentiality, integrity, and authentication: These three are the essential features of the banking sector and were very successfully managed all over the world before the coming of the

internet. Communication across an open and thus insecure channel such as the internet might not be the best base for bank-client relations as trust might partially be lost.

Opportunities of E-Banking

Several Channels: Banks can offer so many channels to access their banking and other services such as ATM, Local branches, Telephone/mobile banking, video banking etc., to increase the banking business.

Bill Payment Services: E-banking can facilitate payment of electricity and telephone bills, mobile phone, credit card and insurance premium bills as each bank has tie-ups with various utility companies, service providers and insurance companies, across the country.

Increasing Internet Users & Computer Literacy: To use internet banking it is a very important or initial requirement that people should know internet technology so that they can easily adopt internet banking services. The fast increasing internet users in India can be a very big opportunity and the banking industry should encash this opportunity to attract more internet users to adopt internet banking services.

Creating high-value digital services to customers: Customer behaviors and expectations have changed radically over the last decade. The trend towards Digital is visible across the board, with the banking industry at the forefront. Customers can access banking services anytime and anywhere, using the channel of their choice. Customers can perform basic banking transactions by simply sitting at their office or home through Smart phone, PC or LAPTOP. Customers can get drafts at their door steps through e-mail call. Thus E-banking facilitates home banking.

Competitive Advantage: The benefit of adopting e-banking provides a competitive advantage to the banks over other players. The implementation of e-banking is beneficial for the bank in many ways as it reduces the cost to banks, improves customer relation, increases the geographical reach of the bank, etc.,. The benefit of e-banking has become opportunities for banks to manage their banking business in a better way.

Competence: Banks can become more efficient than they already are by providing Internet access for their customers. The Internet provides the bank with an almost paper less system. E-banking creates strong basic infrastructure for the banks to embark upon many cash management products and to venture in the new fields like e-commerce, EDI, etc.

Quality Banking: E-banking release innovative vistas for providing well-organized monetary and quality service to the customers. E-banking allows the opportunity of improved quality and an enlarged range of services being made available to the customers.

Conclusion

The e-banking revolution has fundamentally changed the business of banking by scaling borders and bringing about new opportunities. In India also, it has strongly impacted the strategic business considerations for banks by significantly cutting down costs of delivery and transactions. Compared to developed countries, developing countries face many impediments that affect the successful implementation of e-banking initiatives. In this paper, we have identified some such impediments in the Indian context. Thus, all the channels of banking will co-exist with the E-banking facilities. Right now with low and lack of adequate security, infrastructure and internet penetration, it is significant to take necessary actions to enhance E-banking.